

APPROACHES TO THE ECOLOGICAL STUDY OF PASTURES

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Abstract. *This article involves the contents of the scientific work conducted in the pastures, the reports on the restoration of the pastures. The work on the ecological study of pastures and their restoration is shown on the example of some countries.*

Keywords: *pasture, grassland, plant cover, ecosystem, man-made, restoration, adaptive, population*

Introduction. Overgrazing of livestock in natural pastures has a negative effect on the biological diversity of these areas. Domesticated animals, while feeding on pasture plants, do not allow them to reproduce—the plants are not fertilized, so they cannot reproduce. This is crucial for annual plants: if there are no seeds, there will be no plant for the next year.

In natural ecosystems, the number of plant species consumed by livestock decreases, while the number of other plant species that they do not consume, on the contrary, increases and the vegetation cover changes completely. In parallel, as a result of the large number of livestock, the vegetation is simply completely trampled.

Discussion. Ecological studies of pastures and their restoration have been carried out in several countries. Space-based grassland monitoring in New Zealand is explored by Dave Clark, Annette Litherland, Gonzalo Mata, Robert Burling-Claridge. 20% of the farming budget is covered by pastures, and raising this figure to 50% is one of their main goals [9,10].

In California, 52 species of grasslands are managed according to 4 categories. These are: 1. Meadow grass. 2. Broad-leaved grasses. 3. Sour pasture grasses. 4. Irrigated broadleaf pasture [9].

S. Spigal, J. Bartolome and M. Vaytlar analyzed the issues of placing plants in pastures according to their adaptive characteristics for the restoration of California landscapes and developed practical ecological concepts [1; Pp.365-370].

In addition, R. Evitt and J. Bartholomew have studied in detail the issues of preservation of historically formed nature in the development of livestock network, improving the condition of grasslands [2; Pp.1644-1649].

R. Rand, A. Dawson, and J. Bartholomew assessed the plan of action by assessing the current condition of the ecological status and vegetation cover on the coast of Northern California through the density of plants in the surface layer of the soil [1; Pp.464-473.] Also, the analysis of the ecological strategies of survival in plant populations has been studied by scientists such as Gwang, Ganlin and J.London on the example of the San Joaquin Valley. Foreign scientists such as

P. Imbach, M. Manro, E. Barona, G. Gimán and P. Sias study the processes of improper use of pastures around the Amazon and compare their current state. L. Johansen, S. Wen, E. Kallionemi, A. Westin, T. Lennartson, A. Iuga and S. Ivascular developed traditional methods of semi-natural grassland management in agricultural landscapes.

K. Wang, F. Meng, Li X, and S. Wang determined the determinants of initial productivity of grasslands. K. Vancelov, T. Kraudzin and K. Samimilari provided information on cattle grazing and productivity of pastures in Eastern Pamir. B. Abaturov, R. Djapova, E. Ayusheva, V. Djapova, D. Nokhaeva, M. Kolesnikov, V. Minoransky and Yu. Kuznetsov provided scientific information about grazing of camels in pastures and ways of efficient use of pastures. M. Haddad, S. Stromeir, M. Rahbeh, S. Nouvakpo, O. Al-Hamdan, and M. Veltz studied the stages of sustainable land use and degradation.

K. McGwire, M. Weltz, K. Snyder, J. Huntington, C. Morton, and D. McEvoy evaluated early spring cover crop use conditions in Nevada. A. Saparov revealed a sustainable strategy of using sustainable soil and plant resources in the Republic of Kazakhstan. S. Robinson, K. Kerven, R. Behnke, E. Milner-Gulland and K. Kusherov analyzed socio-economic and biophysical characteristics of animal husbandry. I. Alimaev and E. Benkelar justified the stages of mobility and efficient use of land in Kazakhstan. A. Tokusheva, A. Nugmanov and V. Melnikov proposed ways to improve degraded areas in North Kazakhstan based on new technologies. A. Mirzabaev, M. Akhmed, J. Werner, M. Loukhaychi and J. Pender reveal the prospects of efficient use of pastures in the arid regions of Central Asia in their scientific works. L. Kurochkina, K. Karibaeva, A. Bayjumanov, A. Mishchenko, A. Toylibaev, A. Masimov and A. Isabaeva developed recommendations on the management of fodder meadows in the southern Balkhash front areas. L. Dimeeva describes additional criteria for restoration of the anthropogenic ecosystem. S. Lewis, K. Veeler, T. Mitkard and A. Koch revealed in their scientific work that restoration of natural forests is the best way to reduce carbon in the atmosphere. A. Golovanov and F. Ziminlar developed the problems and methods of recultivation of lands in crisis. D. Dzybov applied the methods of accelerated restoration of natural vegetation in agro-steppes. Yu. Gulyanov, G. Yartsev, I. Satunkin and R. Baykasenov revealed the productivity, feeding and fodder characteristics of perennial grasses of the leguminous and wheat families in the southern of Orenburg, Ural regions. N. Gurina, A. Shchirenko and Yu. Rogozina provided information on theoretically based technologies of biological recultivation of disturbed lands in urbanized areas. J. Van Andel and J. Aronson showed the principles of ecological restoration. V. Androkhonov provided information about practical solutions for the recultivation of disturbed lands through an innovative process. And D. Martin revealed the principles of ecological restoration in areas necessary for the 21st century. L. Ivanova, V. Kostina, M. Kremeentskaya and E. Inozemtseva showed the ways of rapid formation of erosion-resistant grasses in man-made areas. S. Mesyats, M. Novojilova and N. Romyantseva studied the genetic characteristics of restoration of degraded lands with the concept of natural soil-formation [7,8].

A. Voronin, L. Lepeshkina, M. Klevtsova, Tu Weiguo, and Guo Xiolin developed the scientific and theoretical basis of ecological restoration of high mountain pastures of western Tibet. J. Benayas, A. Newton, A. Diaz and J. Bullock conducted analysis on biodiversity and ecosystem enrichment through ecological restoration. W. Block, A. Franklin, J. Ward, J. Garney, and G. White assessed the success of ecological restoration and made recommendations for implementation through monitoring. J. Calvo-Alvarado, B. McClennan, A. Sanchez-Azofeifa, and T. Garvin developed a practical and theoretical framework for forest ecology and management in Costa Rica. K. Cheung, D. Libesh and M. Marquez identified some ecological principles and

characteristics of forest restoration in South Brazil.

M. Klaut developed new directions for conservation measures in New Zealand. F. Danielsen, M. Mendoza, A. Tagtag, P. Alviola, D. Balete, A. Jensen, M. Engoff and M. Paulsen analyzed the need to strengthen the protection measures of natural resource management through monitoring. T. Dawson, S. Jackson, J. House, I. Prentiss and G. Maselar carried out scientific work on the preservation of biological diversity during climate change. R. Hobbs and J. Harris carried out scientific work on the ecology of restoration of terrestrial ecosystems in the new millennium and developed practical and theoretical foundations [4,5,6,].

Conclusion. We can conclude that we have analyzed the protection measures of pasture resources through monitoring. On the basis of the reforms carried out in Uzbekistan, programs were developed for the protection of pastures, analysis of the current state of plants spread there, development of protection measures.

In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-46 of December 30, 2021 on measures to accelerate greening in the Republic and more effectively organize tree protection is considered important. Based on this, the decree is important in the implementation of the nationwide green space project.

REFERENCES

1. Spiegel, S., J.W.Bartolome, and M.D.White. 2016. Applying Ecological Site Concepts to Adaptive Conservation Management on an Iconic Californian Landscape. *Rangelands*. 38:365-370.
2. Evett, R.E. and J.W. Bartolome. 2013. Phytolith evidence for the extent and nature of prehistoric Californian grasslands. *The Holocene* 23:1644–1649.
3. Danielsen, F., M.M. Mendoza, A. Tagtag, P.A. Alviola, D.S. Balete, A.E. Jensen, M. Enghoff and M.K. Poulsen (2007); Increasing conservation management action by involving local people in natural resource monitoring, *Ambio*36 (5): 1-5
4. Khujanazarov U. The current state of the pastures of the upper part of the Kashkadarya basin // *Bulletin of the agricultural science of Uzbekistan*. – Tashkent, 2012. – No. 1-2. – Pp. 111-115.
5. Khujanazarov U.E. About the protection of some rare and endemic plant species in the upper part of the Kashkadarya basin // *Reports of the National University of Uzbekistan*. – Tashkent, 2015. – No. 3/2. – Pp. 135-138.
6. Khujanazarov U.E., Karimova N.Sh. Ecological status of some medicinal plants of the southwestern Zarafshan Range // *Reports of the National University of Uzbekistan*. – Tashkent, 2016. – No. 3/1. – Pp. 105-109.
7. Khujanazarov U.E. Ecological status of some endemic plants of the foothills of the Kashkadarya basin // *Reports of the National University of Uzbekistan*. – Tashkent, 2017. – No. 3/2. – Pp. 210-213.
8. Khujanazarov U.E. A statistical analyze of pasture plants of Kashkadarya basin foothills // *European Science Review*. – Vienna, 2017. – №11-12. – Pp. 27-29.
9. <http://www.pasturesfromspace.csiro.au/>. <http://www.fairport.com.au/PastureWatch>, pp.1-16.